

Stakeholders' board structure, communication tools and rules

D2.1

Contact us

www.blurevproject.eu

info@blurevproject.eu

 @BlueRevEU

D2.1

Stakeholders' board structure, communication tools and rules

DELIVERABLE TYPE

R - Report

MONTH AND DATE OF DELIVERY

M3, November 2022

WORK PACKAGE

WP2

LEADER

APRE

DISSEMINATION LEVEL

PU - Public

AUTHOR(S)

Claudia Iasillo (APRE)

DOI / ISBN

10.5281/zenodo.7378172

Programme	Contract Number	Duration	Start
Horizon Europe	101060537	36 Months	September 2022

Contributors

Name

Concetta Maria Messina
Alexandros Koukovinis
Daniel Bengtsson

Organisation

DFBG
LOBA
RISE

Reviewers

Name

Alessio Livio Spera

Organisation

APRE

Revision History

Version	Date	Reviewer	Modifications
0.1	16/11/2022	Claudia Iasillo (APRE)	First version
0.2	28/11/2022	Concetta Maria Messina (DFBG), Alexandros Koukovinis (LOBA), Daniel Bengtsson (RISE)	Comments from partners
1.0	30/11/2022	Claudia Iasillo, Alessio Livio Spera (APRE)	Submitted version

The information and views set out in this report are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union. Neither the European Union institutions and bodies nor any person acting on their behalf.

Table of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Table 1 - Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
APRE	Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
NGOs	Non Governative Associations
SB	Stakeholders' Board
SMEs	Social Medium Enterprises

Index of Contents

1	Executive Summary	8
2	Introduction to BlueRev project	9
3	Stakeholders Engagement in BlueRev	10
3.1	Stakeholders identification	11
3.2	Support tool for stakeholders	13
4	Stakeholders' Board	14
4.1	Stakeholders' board design	14
4.2	Use of the Stakeholders' Board	14
4.3	Data protection	14
4.4	Management of the Stakeholders' Board	15
	Annex 1 Stakeholders' Board template	16
	Annex 2 Guidelines for engaging stakeholders in BlueRev activities.....	17

Index of Tables

Table 1 - Abbreviations and Acronyms	4
Table 2 - Stakeholders' Board structure	16

Index of Figures

Figure 1 - BlueRev concept.....	9
Figure 2 - Preliminary identification of BlueRev Stakeholders Engagement activities..	10
Figure 3 - Stakeholders identification exercise at BlueRev Kick-off Meeting	11
Figure 4 - BlueRev stakeholders categories and change agents.....	12

1 Executive Summary

The current document, titled Stakeholders' board structure, communication tools and rules, has been developed within the framework of the BlueRev project which is funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 101060537.

The document contains the description of the set-up procedures of BlueRev Stakeholders' Board (SB). The set-up of the SB is foreseen by M3 (November 2022) as basis for BlueRev stakeholder engagement activities rooted in the whole project since its early phases.

The main activities of the SB will include providing input on governance, business models and social innovation at regional and local scale; participation in workshops; evaluation of Governance/business models/KPIs/models for social innovations developed within the project.

This document provides an overview of the role of the SB within the project and how the engagement of stakeholders will contribute to project objectives and impacts. Both the structure of the board and how it will be used in the project, in compliance with General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), are described in the first sections of this report.

2 Introduction to BlueRev project

BlueRev project focuses on the revitalisation of European local communities through innovative bio-based business models, governance frameworks and social innovations in the blue bio-based sector, to underline the benefits the wide deployment of the bio-based sector can offer.

To achieve its main objective, BlueRev project will identify and define a range of systems in the blue bio-based sector in 3 different pilot regions throughout Europe (i.e. Denmark, Italy and Estonia) to tailor value chains, from valorisation of co-products as feedstock to processing/conversion to final products, in order to revitalise local communities, both in a territorial and social sense and contribute to positive environmental and social impacts.

The project will first analyse these value chains according to social, economic and environmental barriers and potentialities, business models, local capacities (e.g. feedstocks, infrastructure, human skills, etc.) and innovation actors, including community knowledge and marginalised groups, by using existing or defining improved monitoring system and indicators to evaluate the effectiveness of the value chains. The project will also analyse the existing governance framework and how it can be improved.

The analysis will serve BlueRev to develop or replicate new governance and business models allowing the transition towards socially and environmentally responsible behaviour within all ranges (e.g. regulatory measures, corporate responsibility initiatives, education), to enable sufficient impacts and performances of the specific value chains and to allow replication across Europe.

In doing that BlueRev will ensure an efficient engagement of all actors, including local and regional authorities, primary biomass producers, SMEs, civil society organisations including NGOs, higher education organizations (e.g. universities including blue bioeconomy graduate courses), community knowledge and marginalised groups via robust and transparent communication and awareness-raising campaigns (Figure 1).

Figure 1 - BlueRev concept

3 Stakeholders Engagement in BlueRev

The engagement of stakeholders plays a central role within BlueRev and it is a necessary condition to reach its objectives. A stakeholder is a person representing an organisation or an interest group that has interest in a topic/organisation/project and the outcomes of actions. Moreover, this person and/or the organisation it represents, and/or their stakeholders, is impacted by these outcomes and has some kind of influence in the field.

BlueRev will focus on the **identification of and work with** stakeholders throughout its whole duration. The first action is the definition of the **Stakeholders' Board (SB)**, intended as a database of stakeholders identified by each BlueRev beneficiary (mainly, BlueRev pilot regions) leveraging on their networks and channels, and the establishment of the procedures to manage the SB and make it an effective resource for the whole consortium.

Stakeholders will be actively involved in several project tasks and activities, as depicted in Figure 2), and they will play an important role as **multipliers**, therefore they will need to be informed about BlueRev processes and results (see Section 3.2 Support tool for stakeholders). The SB will serve as basis for the identification of relevant stakeholders to invite to specific project activities (e.g. workshops, interviews, training programme, etc.), according to the activities objectives and the stakeholders expertise, and it will therefore contain information about the stakeholders as detailed as possible. Given that the submission of this deliverable is foreseen at M3 since the start of the project (November 2022), it was a priority to define the SB structure, to be used as a living document throughout the whole project duration by the entire consortium (see Section 4 Stakeholders' Board).

Figure 2 - Preliminary identification of BlueRev Stakeholders Engagement activities

3.1 Stakeholders identification

The stakeholders identification requires the identification of people (representing an organisation or as part of an interest group) who might have interest/influence on or might be impacted by BlueRev activities. A preliminary definition of potential stakeholders includes:

- Other regions/regional bio-based clusters in EU for the future replication of the project results;
- BlueRev beneficiaries' existing networks and channels;
- Relevant projects (e.g. Biobridges, BIOWAYS, BIOVOICES, Transition2Bio, Biogoal, RoadToBio, Power4Bio, InnProBio, CommBeBiz, STARProBio, BioLinX; ProBIO, BioHorizon; PLATFORM2, BIO-STEP, BIOPEN, STAR-4BBI, WASEABI, BIOVECQ, ENGAGE4BIO, BIOLOC, BBC, ARIBIOTEC, etc);
- The European Bioeconomy Network (EuBioNet), a network of EU funded projects about communication, awareness raising, education and stakeholders engagement in the bioeconomy and bio-based sectors)

On the occasion of BlueRev Kick-off Meeting (29th-30th September), it was organized an internal workshop with all Beneficiaries to start defining categories of stakeholders to be engaged in BlueRev. At first, partners were asked to list potential stakeholders, then they were grouped according to the three main lines of analysis within the project (i.e. business, governance and social innovation) with the aim to identify also potential overlaps. Finally, the group worked on the identification of 'change agents', that are a catalyst for change. Stakeholders who are change agents transform businesses by encouraging others to change; for example, by helping to change processes, tools, or behaviours. The stakeholders were then placed on a graph according to their level of influence and their knowledge expertise (Figure 3).

Figure 3 - Stakeholders identification exercise at BlueRev Kick-off Meeting

The exercise led to the identification of the following categories of stakeholders (Figure 4)

- **Governance (policy-makers):** local governance and decision makers, regional authorities, local relevant authorities, local municipalities, regulatory authorities (food and environment), fisheries local action groups and chambers of commerce;
- **Business:** industry, industry bodies, Social Medium Enterprises (SMEs), local businesses, SMEs, Cooperatives, Insurances, Makers/inventors communities, fisheries, pharmaceutical and cosmetic companies and investors;
- **Social innovation:** Employees in the industry, civil society, local Non Governative Associations (NGOs), neighbourhood groups, charity organizations and students;
- **Crossroad:** Academia, Marine Biology Research Centers, Consumers, EU bodies and incubators.

Figure 4 - BlueRev stakeholders categories and change agents

This first exercise to identify categories of stakeholders for the project will be replicated during BlueRev implementation and tailored to the project activities where stakeholders are planned to be involved. BlueRev beneficiaries will be supported by APRE in the definition and engagement of relevant stakeholders (see Annex 2 Guidelines for engaging stakeholders in BlueRev activities).

3.2 Support tool for stakeholders

To keep stakeholders informed, BlueRev will develop the support tool, a web-based platform to facilitate cross-sector collaborations among stakeholders in the value chains of the bio-based economy. The support tool, accessible via BlueRev website, will facilitate the knowledge exchange, enabling to share information about relevant opportunities in the blue bio-based sector and enhancing collaboration opportunities among different stakeholders. Thanks to the support tool, BlueRev stakeholders will also have to opportunity to have first and full access to BlueRev project results, in particular training materials, aimed at building new capacities within the sector. The support tool will be integrated in the project website and thus its structure and detailed functions will be further analyzed in the deliverable of the D6.1 Plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities, foreseen in M6 (February 2022). In line with the descriptions in the Grant Agreement, this platform expansion of the website will bring added value by connecting all the stakeholders under the same collaborative online space, allowing the flow and exchange of critical information for the project success and the exploitation of the Key Exploitable Results.

4 Stakeholders' Board

4.1 Stakeholders' board design

As the data included in the SB will be used for various tasks, the database needs to contain information about stakeholders' interests. For example, the database will provide the required contacts for the organisation of workshops, but also of larger-scale events or dedicated expert groups for small workshops or interviews. In order to make the best use of the database, project partners should have access to the data without any limitations. The SB will include data of all stakeholders identified as relevant for the project and engaged in the project activities (e.g. registered users of BlueRev training programme, T5.2).

The database includes names, surnames, organisation, country, and email of relevant stakeholders. In addition, it includes the source of the information (specifically, BlueRev beneficiary contributing with the information), type of stakeholders, expertise/interest for BlueRev (i.e. governance, business models, social innovation) and a comment field.

Information of private contacts of BlueRev partners that cannot be shared with the whole consortium, will be categorized as "private" contacts (see Section 4.3 Data protection).

4.2 Use of the Stakeholders' Board

The database will initially build on previous contacts established by the consortium members in previous projects and activities. As a first step, the stakeholders database will be filled with contacts from the project partners, as well as from public available contacts. The SB is available on BlueRev SharePoint, accessible to all project partners, and its maintenance is under APRE responsibility, while each Beneficiary is responsible of keeping it regularly updated by adding stakeholders data.

4.3 Data protection

BlueRev SB needs to fulfil European and national regulations on data protection including General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Accordingly, it was therefore decided to apply three different labels to the data contained in the database:

1. **'Name of beneficiary' – public:** applied in the case of the data of the stakeholder are publicly available; all columns in the database will be filled in
2. **'Name of beneficiary' – private:** personal contact of the beneficiary; it will be added to the database but no personal data will be provided.
3. **BlueRev Task X.X registered user:** stakeholders data collected through registration to project's tasks. The protection of the personal data of the

stakeholder will be under the responsibility of Task Leader as detailed in the project consent forms of the specific activity.

In this way, the whole consortium will have access and make the best use of the SB without any infringement of data privacy and protecting the private contacts of each Beneficiary. Indeed, with this scheme, all consortium members will be able to identify a potentially relevant contact, but they will need to refer to the consortium member rightfully holding the personal data details, that will inform the relevant stakeholder about the possibility to be engaged in some project activities and offered the possibility of agreeing to establish contact with the project.

The SB structure is available in Annex 1 Stakeholders' Board template.

4.4 Management of the Stakeholders' Board

The SB is considered a pivotal asset for BlueRev project. Beyond its day to day application meant as a database of relevant contacts, it should also be considered as a living document and resource to identify commonalities and potential synergies among the different stakeholders. With this application in mind and by regularly using it to match the project needs with stakeholders expertise, and vice versa, the SB will contribute to create a network of stakeholders in the blue bio-based sector. In the management of the SB, it will play a central role the Support tool (see Section 4.2 Support tool for stakeholders). The stakeholders will benefit not only of the possibility of having access to project results and resources, but they will also be able to establish contacts with other actors and interact with them.

Annex 1 Stakeholders' Board template

Table 2 - Stakeholders' Board structure

BlueRev Stakeholders' Board								
	Source	Name	Email	Organisation	Org. Country	Type of stakeholders	Expertise for – or interest in – BlueRev (e.g. social innovation, business models, governance)	Comments
ex. 1	APRE Public	John Smith	johnsmith@ec.com	EC	Belgium	Public Institution	Governance	
ex. 2	APRE private	X	X	EC	Belgium	Public Institution	Governance	
ex.3	BlueRev TX.X Registered User	X	X	EC	Belgium	Public Institution	Governance	

Annex 2 Guidelines for engaging stakeholders in BlueRev activities

The first step for working with stakeholders is the **identification** of relevant stakeholders that could be invited to participate to project activities.

The process of identification of stakeholders starts by thinking of which stakeholders could have influence or be impacted by project activities and results. Each beneficiary will start with an analysis of their activities in the project and start listing the stakeholders to be added in the SB. The stakeholders could be divided in:

- **Core Team:** actively involved in the project activities,
- **Involved:** need to be involved in specific activities depending on their expertise or interest,
- **Informed:** will be kept informed and occasionally asked to provide input or feedback on specific points.

For each stakeholders, there are a set of questions each Beneficiary should take into account:

1. What is the stakeholders' primary interest in being involved in BlueRev
2. To what degree would the stakeholder be relevant for BlueRev
3. To what degree would the stakeholder be involved in the process
4. Will the project actions benefit or harm the stakeholder
5. What alliances exist with other stakeholders
6. What conflicts exist with other stakeholders

The second step is the recruitment of stakeholders. For recruitment it is recommended to clearly outline the **value of participation** for stakeholders. For some of them, it is sufficient to raise the awareness that their own reflections and ideas might contribute to project outputs and that their input is inspiring for other stakeholders. For some it might be interesting to become part of wider networks or to spark further ideas in the field. To inform participants about the big picture and interlink them with other stakeholders and activities helps them to reflect on the wider impact. In the recruitment process, APRE and LOBA will help BlueRev partners defining a set of key messages that can be used for governance, business and social innovation categories of stakeholders, focusing on aspects such as the importance of being part of the blue bio-based community to get a voice to be listened and to contribute to the revitalisation of local communities thanks to the benefit offered by the blue bio-based sector. Another important aspect to be considered in the recruitment process is the importance of being clear with the expectations of the project by the commitment of stakeholders, clearly underlining what role they will play in the specific activity Beneficiaries are planning to involve them and what effort will be required.

Bio-based revitalisation
of local communities

Consortium

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

www.blurevproject.eu info@blurevproject.eu

[f](#) [in](#) [t](#) [@](#) [@BlueRevEU](#)

